

THE ORIGIN AND FORMATION OF LEGAL TERMS IN THE UZBEK LANGUAGE: THE EXAMPLE OF COURT-LAW TERMS

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Annotation. There are terms for every field, especially the legal field. Sh. Kochimov expresses the following opinion about the term: "A term is a word (combination of words) that means a special concept related to a certain field and expresses the same meaning in terms of content. Compared to the main parts of words, the term differs in that it expresses a clear and unambiguous concept. This article is devoted to the discussion of the origin and formation of terms related to the field of law in the Uzbek language.

Keywords: language, law, legal society, judicial law, term, legal information, thinking, civil society, legal system, court, authority, crime.

INTRODUCTION

The development of the terminology of a certain language is related to the life of society and the changes taking place in it. Also, the formation of the terminological base of a language is a complex and laborious process, which requires special knowledge and certain skills from its creators, as well as general culture, knowledge, and impeccable literacy. When talking about the law and legal language, legal terminology, it should be noted that the culture of law-making implies strict professional language, as well as its simplicity, comprehensibility and openness to all segments of the population. Inaccuracy of the terms used in the text of the normative-legal document creates the possibility of distorting the meaning of the law. In this regard, H.A. Kerimov expresses the following opinion: "A word or phrase used incorrectly or inappropriately, the difference between an idea and its textual expression can sometimes lead to serious consequences. Especially in the field of law-making." [1, 123] Correct use of legal terms is an integral part of law-making activity. Also, such words are intended to preserve the language of the legislative act and are convenient to use in practice.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Law is the most important regulator of social relations. The most important features of law are formal certainty and binding nature. Formal certainty is expressed in the existence of law and is a process that cannot be imagined without linguistic tools. The effectiveness of legal regulation is largely determined by the quality of regulatory documents, which shows that the role of legislative bodies is very important in them. As noted by the famous Russian jurist I.A. Pokrovsky, "One of the first demands of a developing human personality to the law is the demand for specific legal norms." Moreover, in his opinion, no concept of law can be imagined without the clarity of legal norms. [2, 78]

According to another famous French jurist, F. Jenya, it is only used in law-making and law-enforcement activities. There are special means and methods of embodying legislative thinking in linguistic form. These tools are the basis for distinguishing the independent legislative style of literary speech due to the special tasks before the law, the unique way of

presenting the topic, the special vocabulary of the language to express the legislator's opinion. [3, 167] In legal literature, this style of presentation is described as "law language". When talking about the specific features of the language of legal documents, some authors say that it is the language of law, while others talk about the existence of a special legal language. However, the rule about the specific characteristics of the legal language causes a lot of debates among scientists.

According to the well-known Hungarian jurist I. Szabon, the so-called "legal language" is essentially nothing more than ordinary language filled with special expressions and technical terms, that is, if language tools are used more precisely. E.E., who supported this position. Pryashnikov and E.M. According to Smorgunova, the language of the legislation applies to various spheres of public activity. This feature distinguishes it from languages that have their own vocabulary and special terminology serving a narrowly specialized field. This position is not supported by all authors. Most of them follow the opposite view of socio-legal language. In fact, the legal text will be extended to the widest range of social relations and their subjects. However, naming the existence of a special language in the law does not take into account the specific features of various professional legal activities.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

When presenting the legislative opinion and the form of normative legal documents, it is necessary to comply with certain requirements and use language tools specially developed for the field of law-making. In this regard, the following principles must be strictly followed.

1. Correctly and unambiguously reflect the content of the legal concept;
2. It is not allowed to use unclear, vague terms;
3. Avoid using rhetorical forms and figurative words in the text of the legal document.

Because the terms are not used in the direct and specific sense. This term is always unambiguous and its meaning does not vary according to the text. A word in which there is a semantic uncertainty cannot fulfill the function of expressing a special meaning.

4. In the text of the regulatory legal document, it is desirable to use terms that are widely used and actively used.

5. Stability and instability in the use of legal terminology. It is not appropriate to abandon the traditional terms and introduce new terms that denote the same concepts.

6. Maximum brevity in the use of terms. Terms taken from other languages should not harm the national legal language.

7. Terms made up of two or more words, not to overuse abbreviations. In the language of normative legal documents, it is recommended to use only abbreviations that have a strong place in the literary language.

8. Not using appropriations inappropriately if there is an alternative. Therefore, a legal term is a stable combination of words or words that express the will of the legislator, are used in the same way in the texts of legal documents, and are the generalized name of a legal concept that has a clear meaning. is characterized by functional stability. Nevertheless, the legal terminology of each language system is characterized only by its own characteristics.

The analysis of the quality of local regulatory legal documents and their language is mainly carried out within the framework of the problems of legal (legislative) technology. Most authors consider the development of legal technology as a set of tools, techniques and rules used in the registration and systematization of normative legal documents. [4,231]. In addition, V. N. Kartashov gives a broader interpretation of legal technique. One of the most

important structural elements of legal technique, as an important tool, most researchers turn to legal terminology. A term is a special phrase or symbol adopted in any science or profession. Also, terms are not special words, but special function words.

Each discipline has its own terms. A term means a word or phrase that has a legal meaning in relation to the language of the law. Based on the characteristics and role of legal terms, most authors describe them as the main means of legal technique (legal and technical means). This is certainly the correct description of this phenomenon in legal reality. However, in our opinion, such a description of the terminology is insufficient, because it defines the role and place of the terminology only from one, official legal side.

Legal terms also differ from common words by having the same meaning as above, lack of emotionality, expressiveness.

About the legal term Sh. Kochimov described: "Thus, a legal term is the appearance and name of a certain legal concept, logically expressing a legal meaning and methodologically neutral word or combination of words."

Thus, when we say legal terms, we mean terms consisting of one word, such *sud*, *huquq*, *jinoyat*, etc., but the number of legal terms is also occupied by terms consisting of two words, three or four words.

Considering the classification of these legal terms according to their structure, Sh. Kochimov classifies them as follows: "Observations have shown that in terms of their structure, Uzbek legal terms consist of one, two, three, sometimes four or more words. For example:

1. Terms consisting of two words:

Oliy sud, jinoyat kodeksi, ma'muriy ishlar, oliy jazo, qonunijodkorligi, jinoiy jazo etc.

2. Terms consisting of three words:

jinoyat- qidiruv bo'limi, sudning boshqaruv majlisi, ozodlikdan mahrum etish, qonun chiqaruvchi organ etc.

3. Terms consisting of four words:

tibbiy tUSDagi majburlov choralari, dastlabki huquqiy vaziyatni tiklash (restitutsiya) etc.

4. Terms consisting of five words:

xizmat va hokimiyat vakolatlaridan chetga chiqish, ikki yoki undan ko'p sudlangan shaxs (retsdivist) etc.

The main part of Uzbek legal terms is made up of one and two word terms. Terms consisting of three or more words are very rare.

At this point, it should be noted that when creating the composition of national legal terms, special attention should be paid to the shortest possible structure of terms. Especially, the formation of terms from four or more words is not considered a positive phenomenon in terms. Because such terms make it difficult to understand the legal norms in the text of the normative legal document.

According to G. Gulomova, legal terms are simple and complex according to their structure

divided into types

Based on the above information, we:

- 1) One-component legal terms;
- 2) Two-component legal terms;
- 3) We can classify multi-component legal terms.

One-component legal terms. Legal terms consisting of one word are considered. For example: *qoida, qaror, dublikat, ariza, undirish, belgilash, apillyatsiya, kassatsiya, shikoyat* etc.

Two-component legal terms. Legal terms consisting of two words. In the works of G. Gulomova, it was observed that two-component legal terms are formed in two different forms and they are in the form of 1. Noun + noun and 2. Adjective + noun.

For example: *qonunchilik hujjatlari, davlat boji, majburiy to'lov, mansabdor shaxs, xalqaro shartnoma, konsul yig'ini* etc.

Multi-component legal terms. Such terms include three-component, four-component, five-component and more-component terms.

For example, three-component terms: *ma'muriy huquqiy faoliyat, davlat boshqaruv organi, hal qiluv qarori, nazorat tartibidagi shikoyat, chet davlat sudi, yakka tartibdagi tadbirkorlik, majburiy ijro etish, davlat ro'yxatidan o'tkazish* etc.

Four component terms: *yuridik ahamiyatga molik ishlar, nazarda tutilganidan boshqacha qoidalar, fuqarolik ishi bo'yicha sudlar, alohida tartibda yuritiladigan ishlar, harakatlar uchun vakolatli muassasalar, chet davlat hokimlik sudi* etc.

Terms with five or more components: *ish yuritishni tugatish to'g'risidagi ajrim, fuqarolarning o'zini-o'zi boshqarish organi, idoraviy normativ-huquqiy hujjat, sud jarimalarini solish to'g'risidagi ajrim, davoni ko'rmasdan qoldirish to'g'risidagi ajrim, mustaqil talablar bilan arz qiluvchi* etc.

It should be noted that when the terms were defined, it was mainly a word or a combination of words. Multi-componentism is considered a negative phenomenon, but in order to fully understand a certain legal concept, such a phenomenon is allowed.

For example, let's pay attention to the interpretation of court terms in **sud** and **fuqarolik ishi**.

Sud- criminal civil, administrative, etc. the state body that reviews and resolves cases of this category" is considered. If this term gives the concept of a general court, the term court in a civil case appears as a private, that is, a type of court. We explain this term in connection with the term civil case as follows.

Fuqarolik ishi bo'yicha sud – a court that considers cases aimed at resolving disputes about the rights protected by law and related subjective civil rights of citizens and legal entities.

These two terms differ from each other, first of all, in terms of their structure, and then in terms of generality-specificity. The term **Sud** gives the concept of courts in the general sense, and its types are mentioned in the explanation. In our second term, it is private, and it means only court related to civil cases. It is for this reason that multi-component terms are allowed to be used.

Terms of the language of one-component arrows	Two-component decision language terms	Multicomponent decision language terms
<p>ariza, qoida, qaror, undirish, apillyatsiya, belgilash, kassatsiya, shikoyat, dublikat, arbitraj harakatlari, nizolashish, harakatsizligi, da'vo, jarima, ajrim, dublikat, notarius, konsul, dalolatnoma, guvoynoma, ruxsatnoma, rasmiylashtirmoq, vakolatxona, viza, jinoyat, akkreditatsiya, nikoh, rasmiylashtirmoq, alimen...,</p>	<p>davlat boji, qonun hujjatlari, xalqaro shartnoma, mansabdor shaxs, majburiy to'lov, konsul yig'ini, ozod qilish, tartibga solish, xalqaro shartnoma, amalga oshirish, konsullik muassalari, konsullik harakatlari, patent boji, vakolatli muassasa, yuridik shaxs, jismoniy shaxs, murojaat qilmoq, da'vo arizalari, ijro varaqasi, hakamlik sudi, ro'yxatidan o'tkazish, rad etganlik, bo'yin tovlaganlik, ko'chirma nusxa, fuqarolik holati, biometrik passport, diniy tashkilot, muomalaga layoqatsiz, hukm qilmoq, moddiy zarar</p>	<p>three component terms: davlat boshqaruv organi, ma'muriy huquqiy faoliyat, nazorat tartibidagi shikoyat, hal qiluv qarori, majburiy ijro etish, chet davlat sudi, yakka tartibdagi tadbirkorlik, davlat ro'yxatidan o'tkazish, fuqaroligi bo'lmagan shaxs, biometrik yo'l hujjati, yakka tartibdagi tadbirkor, nodavlat notijorat tashkilot, ozodlikdan mahrum qilish, jinoiy javobgarlikkatortganlik, Four component terms: nazarda tutilganidan boshqacha qoidalar, yuridik ahamiyatga molik ishlar, harakatlar uchun vakolatli muassasalar, fuqarolik ishi bo'yicha sudlar, alohida tartibda yuritiladigan ishlar, chet davlat hokimlik sudi, kirish huquqini beruvchi hujjat, taklif qilish to'g'risida hujjat, Terms with five or more components: fuqarolarning o'zini-o'zi boshqarish organi, ish yuritishni tugatish to'g'risidagi ajrim, davoni ko'rmasdan qoldirish to'g'risidagi ajrim, sud jarimalarini solish to'g'risidagi ajrim, idoraviy normativ-huquqiy hujjat, mustaqil talablar bilan arz qiluvchi qonunga xilof ravishda hukm etganlik</p>

It should be noted that the series of legal terms consists mainly of terms with one or two components. The component of multi-component terms consists of these terms, and unclear situations that need an explanation serve as a factor in the emergence of multi-component terms.

Also Sh. According to the field of use of Kochimov terms:

1. General legal terms;

2. Terms of constitutional law;
3. Terms of administrative law;
4. Civil law terms;
5. Criminal law terms;
6. Terms of land rights;
7. Terms of agrarian law;
8. Labor law terms;
9. Terms of social security law;
10. Environmental law terms;
11. Terms of financial law;
12. Terms of civil procedural law;
13. Terms of criminal-procedural law;
14. International law terms.

CONCLUSION

To sum up, the question of classification is still one of the problematic situations of legal terminology. Tried to clarify. In addition, the classification of legal terms according to their structure is a bit painful. These two problems have not been solved yet. There are variations in the literature. In order to solve this problem, we tried to clarify this season to make our contribution.

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